

REPUBLIC OF TÜRKİYE

MARMARA UNIVERSITY

FACULTY OF BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION

DEPARTMENT OF MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS (ENGLISH)

**ANALYSIS OF MARKET SHOPPING HABITS USING CLUSTERING
TECHNIQUES:**

A COMPARATIVE STUDY BETWEEN TURKEY AND THE UNITED STATES

Bachelor's Thesis

Muhammed Yusuf Lale

Istanbul, 2025

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Advisor: Dr. Dilara Büyükköz

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GENERAL INFORMATION

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ABSTRACT

This study look how people spend money in Turkey and USA in year 2011. First, we clean the data and fix category names so they same. We also make numbers more fair by using standardize.

Then we use PCA to make data more small and easy to see. After that, we use K-Means to make groups. We try 2 groups and 3 groups for each country.

We check if groups are good with some scores like Silhouette, Davies-Bouldin, and Calinski-Harabasz.

Result show some people spend money same, but some different. This maybe help company or others understand how people spend.

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This thesis is end of a long but nice learning time. I studied how people in Turkey and USA spend money, and I used some computer methods that don't need labels (unsupervised stuff). During this, some people helped me a lot.

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Summary

This study looks at how families in Turkey and USA spend money. It uses a method called K-Means and also PCA to find groups in my data. Goal is to see what kind of households spend in similar or different ways by looking at what they spend on.

Data comes from public sources and shows spending in 2011. Before using model, we cleaned data. We fixed big values using Winsor method and made numbers on same scale by standardizing. PCA helped to make data smaller.

We tried making 2 and 3 groups and then checked which one is better. We used scores like Silhouette, Davies-Bouldin, Calinski-Harabasz, and Dunn to see if groups are close inside and far from each other.

Results showed Turkish families spend more on basic needs, but in USA, people spend more in many areas. We gave names to groups like "Basic Needs", "Balanced", and "Social Spenders" to describe them.

These results help us understand more about how different people spend money, and how we can use clustering to compare countries.

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation Full Term

AI	Artificial Intelligence
CH Index	Calinski–Harabasz Index
DBI	Davies–Bouldin Index
DI	Dunn Index
GMM	Gaussian Mixture Models
K	Number of Clusters
MSE	Mean Squared Error
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
SS	Silhouette Score
SSE	Sum of Squared Errors
TSI	Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK)
U.S.	United States
Z-score	Standard Score (used for normalization and outlier detection)
WCSS	Within-Cluster Sum of Squares (used in Elbow Method, equivalent to SSE)

Abbreviation Full Term

PC1 / PC2	Principal Component 1 / Principal Component 2 (axes from PCA transformation)
IQR	Interquartile Range (used in outlier detection)
DBSCAN	Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise
CES	Consumer Expenditure Survey (conducted by BLS in the U.S.)
BLS	Bureau of Labor Statistics (U.S.)
k	Cluster Count (hyperparameter in K-Means and other clustering algorithms)
L1 / L2	Manhattan Distance (L1) / Euclidean Distance (L2)

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1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and Significance of Study

This study tries to see, if we can find like hidden ways people use their money. We use K-Means and PCA, which are like computer tools. It looks at Turkey and also USA — they not same in how people live. We want to see if we can group them by how they spend. Maybe this help for making rules, or market stuff, or just knowing more about people.

When we know how families use money, it helps many. Like, government can make better plans. Companies can maybe sell better. And people who study this can see, like, life and money together. Today, everything is more personal, and we want smart choices. So clustering gives us more small group ideas, not just big country numbers.

This work also matter 'cause we compare two countries, not just one. Many times people just use income for groups. But here, we look at how they spend, not how much they have. Also we take same year, 2011, for both, and fix spending types so they match. That way, it's more fair to compare.

1.2. Literature Review

People use clustering in lots of areas like market stuff, pattern finding, or when they study people and groups. It's helpful when there's no labels in data. It works good 'cause it finds hidden things in big and hard data, like when people spend money or live different based on where they from or who they are. (Jain et al., 2000).

K-Means is maybe most known clustering method. It's simple to run on computer and works well when you want to find small, clear groups that don't mix. It does this by trying to keep points in each group close to each other.(Jain, 2010). We use this method a lot in economy, I mean like to see how people spend money. But it has some limits of course. It thinks all groups are round and doesn't like strange points. So, when data is more messy, other methods like DBSCAN, Hierarchical Clustering, or Gaussian Models are used instead.(Aggarwal, 2015; Guyeux et al., 2019).

Sometimes we use PCA with clustering to make things to understand. PCA takes data with many values and turns it into a small set. It does to keep important stuff. It shows which parts of data matter most and hides extra noise that doesn't help much. (Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016; Shlens, 2014) . In data about how families spend money, PCA really helps. It shows main things people spend on and helps us see some common habits or patterns in their behavior. (James et al., 2017)

To check if clustering worked well, I found researchers use some scores. One of them is Silhouette Score — it tells how close points are inside group and how far from other groups (Lletí et al., 2004). There is also Davies-Bouldin Index and Calinski-Harabasz Index. Two of them look at how tight the clusters are and how far apart they are (Fu et al., 1977; Milligan & Cooper, 1985). Another is Dunn Index. It checks bad cases too, for example when clusters are not clear or too close to each other (Dunn & Fostick, 1974).

Some studies used clustering on spending data. For example, (Liu et al., 2010) talked about how important it is to check quality of clusters, especially when data has many variables. (Euzenat & Shvaiko, 2013) looked at how to match meanings in tasks that don't have labels. (Lletí et al., 2004) worked for cluster quality.

Good example of using clustering in Turkey is (Büyükköz, 2010), She used fuzzy clustering for look at differences between Turkey and EU countries. Her work was based on ideas from socio-economic studies. It showed that fuzzy methods are good when people's spending habits. She also found that each country had its own spending style.

Cross-country comparisons are not so common in older studies, but more people are starting to use them now. (Jain, 2010) said that if we want to compare countries fairly, we need to use same format for spending data and also do some steps before clustering. In this thesis, spending is shown as percentages, which helps to remove effect of income. So, we can compare how people behave, not just how much money they have (Tan et al., 2018).

Before clustering, it's important to clean and fix data. For example standardization, winsorization, and choosing good features help. (Maguire, 2006; S. B. Kotsiantis et al., 2006). If we don't do these steps, model can focus on bad values instead of real spending behavior.

One more thing: we can't forget big economy picture. Countries are different in how people spend. Reports from (OECD, n.d.) say that people in U.S. usually spend more on health and houses, but in Turkey, families spend more on food and school stuff (Çatık & Karaçuka, 2012; Denavas-Walt & Proctor, 2015; OECD, n.d.). So, when we look at groups from clustering, we should remember these country differences.

1.3. Data

1.3.1. Data Sources and Description

In this work, we use 2 dataset — one from Turkey and one from USA. Both are from 2011. They show how much households spend on different things, but in percent form, not real money. Data is split by family types, like small or big families. I use info for work and compare and make groups.

1.3.1. Turkey Household Expenditure Dataset (2011)

Data from Turkey comes from TÜİK. File name is called “Hanehalkı tipinin hanehalkı tüketim harcamasının türlerine göre dağılımı”. I mean how different household types spend their money. It shows spending in percentages. For example how much spendin to food, housing, transport,

health, school, and more. Data is split with family types, examples one-person homes, nuclear families, or big extended families.

1.3.2. United States Consumer Expenditure Dataset (2011)

U.S. data comes from Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS). It's part of Consumer Expenditure Survey (CES) for 2011. File is called cusize.xls and shows how much different types of households spend in percentages. Household sizes include single people, couples, and families with 3 or more members. Spending is divided into parts like housing, transport, food, health, school, fun, and other stuff.

1.3.3. Preprocessing Notes

Firstly datasets cleaned and prepared to make them easier. Spending percentages were standardized so everything would be on same. If there were any none value, I will fill in by using average of column. Very large or very small numbers could harm results too much were fixed by using Winsorization. Then, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was used to reduce number of variables and make groups easier to see. After, datasets became more similar in structure, so I can made it possible to compare how households in Turkey and U.S. spend money, also two countries are very different.

1.4. Structure of Thesis

Thes has six parts for help explain how households in Turkey and U.S. spend money, using clustering. First part gives introduction. It is about why study is important, what other studies have said, what kind of data is used.

Second part shows something about data science. For example ideas like clustering, how K-Means and K-Medoids work, how PCA helps to make data, and how we choose number of groups and test if groups are good.

Third part focuses on how data was prepared before analysis. It explains how spending categories were made similar, how numbers were normalized and standardized.

Fourth part shows how analysis was done. It includes data importing, transforming, applying PCA, and work K-Means clustering with 2 and 3 clusters. It shows how results visualized.

2. Data Science

2.1. Clustering

Data mining is finding useful informations in data. It's important for people in business who want to make better choices. Something done in data mining are grouping, things into types making predictions, and making groups (Han et al., 2011).

Figure 2.1.1. Data mining process from data collection to knowledge extraction.
(Source:(Han et al., 2011). Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques, 3rd ed., p. 9)

Clustering is method in machine learning. I can say group things based on their features. It doesn't need any labels before . Things that are similar go into same group, and different ones stay together. I mean this can used in many areas like marketing, pictures, and health (Tan et al., 2018).

Figure 2.1.3. PCA-based dimensionality reduction for cluster visualization.

(Source: (Han et al., 2011). Data Mining: Concepts and Techniques (3rd ed., p. 385).

2.2. Clustering Analysis

Clustering is main method in machine learning when no labels in data. It puts similar things together. People use it in psychology, biology, numbers, and computers (Jain et al., 2000).

Classification needs known answers. Clustering not need that. It just looks at data and finds groups by itself (Tan et al., 2018).

When clustering is done, we get groups. Inside one group, things are close. Between groups, things are different. We look at distance to see if they close. Groups can look like circle, oval, or strange shape.

Clustering makes big data smaller. It helps us see and understand better. It is a bit like other methods too. One groups people. One groups variables. (Hastie et al., n.d.).

2.3. K-Means Algorithm and Clustering Fundamentals

K-Means is a popular clustering method. It splits data into groups with low internal variance. Each point goes to cluster with closest center by Euclidean distance. (Han et al., 2011; Tan et al., 2018).

Distance between point X_i and cluster center Y_j uses squared Euclidean norm:

$$\text{Dist}(X_i, Y_j) = \|X_i - Y_j\|^2$$

This shows how well point fits in its cluster. Algorithm goal, called Sum of Squared Errors (SSE), is calculated like this:

$$SSE = \sum_{j=1}^K \sum_{x_i \in C_j} \|x_i - y_j\|^2$$

(K): number of clusters, and (C_j) shows set of

data points in cluster (j). Each (x_i) is a point within that cluster, and

(y_j) is the shows centroid

In each step, centroids change by averaging positions of points in group. This gives name to method: K-Means (James et al., 2017).

2.3.1 Mahalanobis K-Means Variation

Mahalanobis uses data's covariance with finding distance (Hastie et al.). It changes Euclidean with Mahalanobis distance.(Hastie et al., n.d.).

Formula:

$$\text{Dist}(X_i, Y_j) = (X_i - Y_j)^T \Sigma_j^{-1} (X_i - Y_j)$$

Where:

X_i is an individual data point,

Y_j is the centroid of cluster C_j ,

Σ_j is covariance matrix of cluster C_j , estimated from assigned points,

Σ_j^{-1} adjusts distance based on shape and orientation.

This helps when clusters are not round — for example, when they are long or dense in parts — because it adapts to data shape.

But Mahalanobis K-Means still fails on hard shapes like non-convex clusters. In those cases, density-based methods like DBSCAN work better (Tan et al., 2018).

2.4. K-Medoids and K-Medians Clustering Approaches

2.4.1 K-Medoids Algorithm and Medoid-Based Clustering

K-Means uses average of points as center, but this is sensitive to noise. K-Medoids is stronger for such issues. It picks real data points we say medoids, as centers. (Kaufman & Rousseeuw, 1990).

We have four key steps:

Step 1 – Assignment: Give each point to group with closest medoid, based on chosen distance rule.

$$x_i \in C_j \text{ such that } \text{Dist}(x_i, y_j) = \min_{1 \leq j \leq k} \text{Dist}(x_i, y_j)$$

Where:

x_i : A data point in dataset D

C_j : j -th cluster

y_j : medoid (representative) of cluster C_j

$\text{Dist}(x_i, y_j)$: distance between data point x_i and medoid y_j

k : total number of clusters

Step 2 – Cost: Add up distances from all points to their medoids for total cost.

$$\text{TotalCost} = \sum_{j=1}^k \sum_{x_i \in C_j} \text{Dist}(x_i, y_j)$$

Where:

TotalCost: Total cost of clustering configuration

x_i : A data point in dataset D

y_j : medoid (representative) of cluster C_j

C_j : j - th cluster

$\text{Dist}(x_i, y_j)$: distance between data point x_i and medoid y_j

k : total number of clusters

Step 3 – Swap: Try changing medoid with another point. If this lowers total cost, we can make swap.

If $\text{TotalCost}_{\text{new}} < \text{TotalCost}_{\text{current}}$, then replace y_j with x_i

Where:

$\text{TotalCost}_{\text{new}}$: total cost after replacing current medoid with a new candidate

$\text{TotalCost}_{\text{current}}$: current total cost before replacement

y_j : current medoid of cluster C_j

x_i : A candidate data point from dataset D

C_j : j - th cluster

Step 4 – Result: If no better swap is found, we can stop. Show final groups and their medoids.

Return $\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$ and $\{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_k\}$

Where:

C_j : j -th cluster containing a subset of data points

y_j : medoid (representative data point) of cluster C_j

k : total number of clusters

2.4.2 K-Medians Algorithm and Manhattan Distance Clustering

K-Medians works like K-Means, but uses Manhattan distance (L_1) instead of Euclidean (L_2). It works better with outliers or unbalanced data (Aggarwal, 2015). Goal is to cut down total absolute gap between points and group centers.

Manhattan Distance Formula (L₁ Norm):

$$\text{Dist}(X_i, Y_j) = |X_i - Y_j|_1$$

Where:

X_i is a data point in the dataset

Y_j is the median - based representative of cluster C_j

$|X_i - Y_j|_1$ denotes the Manhattan (L1) distance

Total L₁ Error Function

$$L_{1_Error} = \sum_{j=1}^K \sum_{X_i \in C_j} |X_i - Y_j|_1$$

Where:

L_{1_Error} represents total clustering cost

K : total number of clusters

X_i is a data point assigned to cluster C_j

Y_j : median point (cluster center) of C_j

$|X_i - Y_j|_1$: Manhattan distance between X_i and Y_j

K-Means uses average as center. K-Medians picks median on each axis. This works because median gives smallest total gap in one-dimensional case:

$$\text{In 1D: } \text{median}(x) = \arg \min_y \sum_i |x_i - y|$$

Where:

x_i are values in cluster

y : candidate center value

$$\sum_i |x_i - y| : \text{total L1 deviation}$$

In multi-feature data, K-Medians finds median for each feature one by one. But this median point often does not match a real sample in data. This is different from K-Medoids, which always picks real data points (Tan et al., 2018) because we use median, K-Medians handles outliers better and shows center more clear in unbalanced data. It works well on noisy or skewed datasets (Hastie et al., n.d.).

2.5. Determining Optimal Number of Clusters: Elbow Method

One hard part in clustering is picking right number of groups (k). Too few groups miss patterns (underfitting), too many cause overfitting and noise problems. Elbow rule helps choose k. It looks at WCSS (Within-Cluster Sum of Squares), also we say SSE, for different k values (Han et al., 2011; Jain, 2010). This shows how close points are to their centers — lower means tight groups.

SSE:

$$\text{SSE} = \sum_{j=1}^K \sum_{x_i \in C_j} |x_i - y_j|^2$$

Where:

SSE: Total within - cluster sum of squared errors

K : Total number of clusters

x_i : data point assigned to cluster C_j

C_j : j - th cluster

y_j : Centroid of cluster C_j

$|x_i - y_j|^2$: Squared Euclidean distance between x_i and y_j

How Elbow Method Works:

1. Run K - Means clustering for a range of cluster counts (e.g., $k = 1$ to 10).
2. For each of k , calculate corresponding SSE.
3. Plot k on x - axis and SSE on y - axis.
4. Look for *elbow* point — SSE starts to decrease slowly.

This point suggests optimal trade - off between simplicity and accuracy.

2.6. Dimensionality Reduction Techniques

2.6.1 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a way to shrink data size while keeping important changes in it (Han et al., 2011; Jolliffe & Cadima, 2016) . It turns high-dimensional data into new axes, we call principal parts. These axes show most change, and each new one adds new info without repeating old one.

PCA makes data easier to view and use. It also removes noise and extra info, that's why clustering works better. Next part shows how to check if groups found by clustering are useful and clearly split.

1. *normalized data matrix*

$$X \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times p}$$

2. *PCA seeks a linear projection*

$$Y = XW$$

3. *W is matrix of eigenvectors of covariance matrix of X*

$$W = [w_1, w_2, \dots, w_p]$$

4. *Covariance matrix of X*

$$\Sigma = (1/n) \cdot X^t X$$

5. *Eigenvector equation*

$$\Sigma w_i = \lambda_i w_i$$

6. *Eigen values are sorted in descending order*

$$\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \dots \geq \lambda_p$$

7. *Each λ_i represents variance explained by PC_i (Shlens, 2014)*

Figure 2.6.1.1. Principal Components Analysis visualization.

(Source: (Han et al., 2011), 2012, p. 103)

2.7. Cluster Validity Measures and Evaluation Metrics

2.7.1 Silhouette Score (SS)

SS shows how well clustering worked. Unlike methods that check only closeness inside a group (like SSE), it also checks how far groups are from each other. This makes it more balanced (Kaufman & Rousseeuw, 1990) .

For point i, score is:

$$s(i) = \frac{b(i) - a(i)}{\max(a(i), b(i))}$$

Where:

a(i): Avg. distance to same cluster points.

b(i): Avg. distance to nearest other cluster.

This means:

High a(i) → weak cohesion.

Low b(i) → poor separation.

s(i) ≈ 1 → well – clustered.

s(i) ≈ 0 or < 0 → overlap/misclassified.

Clustering can be checked by see how close points are inside group and how far they stay from another one. Average SS helps for it. If value goes over 0.5, groups look clear and well made (Kaufman & Rousseeuw, 1990). A range for example 0.35 to 0.5 is still okay, especially when data has many features or some noise (Guyeux et al., 2019; Lletí et al., 2004). However when score down under 0.3, it often shows that groups mix or have unclear borders (Liu et al., 2010). In fact, 0.35 is often picked as a good lower point for social cases.

2.7.1.1 Intra-cluster Cohesion and Inter-cluster Separation

Clustering quality often depends on two ideas: how close points are inside each group (cohesion) and how far groups stay from one another (separation). Strong cohesion means points in one group stay near each other and near group center. Good separation means groups are far apart, with little to no mix between them. A strong clustering result shows both—tight groups and clear space between them. These ideas support many scoring methods like SS, Davies–Bouldin Index, and Calinski–Harabasz Index (Tan et al., 2018).

2.7.2 Davies–Bouldin Index

Davies–Bouldin Index (DBI) is one way to measure clustering from inside. It checks how compact groups are and how far apart they stay. Goal is to get groups with low spread inside, but high distance between each other (Fu et al., 1977).

DBI Formula:

R_{ij} formula:

$$R_{ij} = \frac{S_i + S_j}{M_{ij}}$$

R_i :

$$R_i = \max_{j \neq i} R_{ij}$$

\bar{R}

$$\bar{R} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N R_i$$

Where:

S_i = average distance of points in cluster i to its centroid

M_{ij} = distance between centroids of clusters i and j

$R_i = \max_{j \neq i} R_{ij}$ (captures worst - case similarity of cluster i)

\bar{R} = average of R_i

Lower values \bar{R} of indicate more compact and well-separated clusters (Fu et al., 1977).

Figure 2.7.2.1. – Cluster changes with Davies–Bouldin Index

(a) Two-dimensional view of data, showing clear groups. Each group may form one cluster.

(b) Graph of DB Index \bar{R} vs. cluster count (k), shown for $q = 0.5, 1.0,$ and 2.0 . Lower \bar{R} means better result. Graph shows that quality gets better first, then stays flat.

(c) Cluster shapes for $k = 8$ and $k = 9$. Even small change in k shifts borders and affects group meaning. Based on (Fu et al., 1977) (p. 225).

Figure 2.7.2.2. – Cluster control on Hierarchical Data with Davies–Bouldin Index

(a) Scatter plot shows groups with different sizes and shapes. (b) DB Index \bar{R} shown against cluster count (k), with $q = 1.0$. \bar{R} drops fast at first, after that moves up and down, Suggestion is possible best k values at low points. (c) Cluster lines shown for $k = 3, 6, 10,$ and 13 . As k grows, borders and shapes change, showing how group structure shifts in layered data. Based on (Fu et al., 1977) (p.226).

2.7.3 Calinski–Harabasz Index

Calinski–Harabasz Index, also called Variance Ratio Criterion, is an internal score used to judge clustering. It compares how far groups are from each other with how tight points are inside each group. This shows both separation and compactness. Method was first introduced by (Caliński & Harabasz, 1974) and helps find good cluster count without using labeled data.

CHI:

$$CH(k) = \frac{\text{Tr}(B_k)}{\text{Tr}(W_k)} \cdot \frac{n-k}{k-1}$$

Where:

$\text{Tr}(B_k)$ = trace of between - cluster dispersion matrix

$\text{Tr}(W_k)$ = trace of within - cluster dispersion matrix

n = total number of data points

k = number of clusters

$\text{Tr}(B_k)$ shows how far cluster centers are from data center. $\text{Tr}(W_k)$ shows how close points are within each group. Bigger CH score means better result — more space between groups and tighter structure inside.

This index works well with others like DBI or SS. DB Index focuses on overlap and local shape. CHI looks more at overall spread and structure of data (Milligan & Cooper, 1985).

Figure 2.7.3.1 – Calinski–Harabasz Index for Choosing Cluster Count

Chart shows CH index for different values of k. Score peaks at k = 4, suggesting best group structure at this point. After that, values drop, showing weaker clustering results.

2.7.5. Dunn Index

Dunn Index (DI) is a common way to judge clustering quality in unsupervised learning. First introduced by (Dunn & Fosdick, 1974), this score favors groupings that are tight inside and far from each other. Good clustering under DI means each group is compact, and groups are clearly apart.

$$DI = \frac{\min_{1 \leq i < j \leq k} d(C_i, C_j)}{\max_{1 \leq l \leq k} \delta(C_l)}$$

Where:

$d(C_i, C_j)$: distance between clusters C_i and C_j

$\delta(C_l)$: diameter of cluster C_l

k = number of clusters

Higher DI means better result — more space between groups and less spread inside. Unlike DBI, which punishes overlap, DI rewards bigger gaps and tight shape.

In this work, DI supports other scores for example SS, DB Index, and Calinski–Harabasz by giving more geometric view. This fits well with K-Means, where groups are often assumed to be separate and convex in Euclidean space (Han et al., 2011).

DI reacts to noise and changes with distance rule used (Kovács, Legány, & Babos, 2005), it still gives helpful results — especially when data has simple group shapes based on space and form (Han et al., 2011; Kovács et al., n.d.).

2.8. Tools and Software Used

Python (v3.10): Language for all tasks — Good for simple syntax and powerful data tools.

Pandas: Helped reshape tables, join documents, and fix missing values in data.

NumPy: It has got fast math operations and matrix steps.

Scikit-learn: Used for K-Means, PCA, scaling features, and scores like Silhouette and Calinski–Harabasz.

Matplotlib & Seaborn: Made visuals like elbow curves, cluster maps, and silhouette plots for easy reading.

Jupyter / Spyder: Jupyter helped with quick testing; Spyder worked well for full script writing with version control.

Microsoft Excel: Used early on to check and format raw spending money tables from Turkey and U.S.

3. Data Preprocessing

3.1. Data Preprocessing Meaning

Preparing data is really important. In Machine data mining, this step is very critic (Han et al., 2011). If data looks better and is more clear, models usually work better and give results with logical.

Raw data isn't always clean. It can have missing values, errors and of course noise. If nothing changes, these problems can damage results. In addition model will be less accurate (S. B. Kotsiantis et al., 2006).

Data Preprocessing Steps are:

- **Data cleaning**
- **Data integration**
- **Data transformation**
- **Data reduction**

Each of step working with data and using original values. (Jain et al., 2000).

In clustering, there are no labels. That's why, model has to figure things out on its own. If data is messy or has too many columns, it can mess up distance metrics. Then, patterns won't show clearly. That's why cleaning data helps a lot. It makes results easier to trust, both in simple tests and bigger ones too (Jain et al., 2000).

3.2 Matching and Harmonizing Categories

Data can come from many places, so labels not always same. One file use short names, another use long or detailed ones. That mix can make it messy. To fix, people working with data try to match labels. This thing called category harmonization.

It not only technical fix. It's needed for making results more clear and easier to check. Very useful when comparing. If labels don't match well, it can confuse things and hard to believe result when data comes from different sources (Maguire, 2006).

To fix these, data people often use what they know and match stuff by hand. Sometimes, they use list with standard words to keep names same. When it's more difficult, they might use ontology tools. These can link close terms even if words look different (Euzenat & Shvaiko, 2013). This kind of help is good when data is big and has mixed structure.

3.3 Normalization and Standardization

Normalization and standardization are well known ways to prepare numbers in dataset. Main goal is to make values stay on similar scale. This matters a lot for models that use distance for example clustering. If we do not use same scale results sometimes can be wrong

Normalization puts values into fixed range. Distance is 0 to 1. It can work good when scales are different. (Han et al., 2011). Standardization makes numbers go around 0. To do this, we take average, then divide by how much numbers change (James et al., 2017).

These steps stop big numbers from changing outcome too much. K-Means and similar methods need this kind of scaling. If not done, centroids can move to wrong spots, hurting model quality (Jain et al., 2000)

Which one to pick depends on data. Normalization helps when range is known. Standardization fits better when data looks like normal curve. Also less affected by extreme values.(Tan et al., 2018).

Shortly, both help features stay balanced. This makes clustering clearer and model work better.

Figure 3.3.1 – Simple View of Raw, Normalized, and Standardized Data.

This chart compares three versions of same data. Left side shows original values. Middle part shows data scaled between 0 and 1 using min-max method. Right side shows values changed with standardization, where numbers go around 0 and spread more evenly.

3.4. Outlier Detection and Winsorization

Outliers are unrealistic and different values in dataset . They may come from mistakes. These values can hurt models. If we use distance for example K-Means (Han et al., 2011).

Clustering is very sensitive to outliers. If outliers available in data, they can move cluster centers and make results too worse (Jain et al., 2000).

To find outliers, people often use IQR rule or Z-score. Also Boxplots and scatterplots also help visualise values. After finding them, we can remove or change them (Tan et al., 2018).

One method is Winsorization. This does not delete values. It just pushes extreme ones closer to normal range. This way, data shape stays same, but bad effects get smal and invisible. Trimming removes data, but Winsorization only adjusts (Ghosh & Vogt, n.d.).

By using methods like this, we can reduce problems from outliers. This can make clustering more stable.

Figure 3.4.1. – Boxplot Highlighting Outliers

This boxplot shows how values are spread. Points outside lines are outliers, found using IQR rule. This kind of chart helps spot extreme values before clustering.

4. Implementation and Evaluation

4.1. Data Import and Pivoting

4.1.1. Turkey Dataset

First dataset shows how different household types in Turkey spent money in 2011. It gives spending percentages across many categories. Goal is to understand how families split money between basic needs and extra items.

Data came from Excel, loaded with Pandas. Main columns were:

- Country
- Year
- Household Type
- Expenditure Type
- Percentage

After loading, data was reshaped using pivot. New format turned data into table for clustering.

- Each row: one household type (like single adult, couple with kids)
- Each column: one spending category (like food, housing, transport)
- Each cell: percent of money that group spent money on category

An excerpt from the pivoted structure is shown below:

Table 4.1.1.1 – Pivoted Household Expenditure Matrix for Turkey (2011)

Household Type	Food	Housing	Health	Transportation	...
Single adult	23.1	29.5	7.0	12.8	...
Couple with children	21.7	31.2	5.4	15.9	...
Extended family	22.3	33.4	6.3	10.2	...

Thi

s table gives how different households in Turkey spent money (2011)

- Rows: household types for example single adult or large family.
- Columns: spendings for example food, housing, or transport.
- Numbers: percent of money each group used for each category.

This format makes data easy. It helps compare spending habits across household types in a simple way.

4.1.2 United States Dataset

Second dataset shows how households in United States spent money in 2011. Like Turkish data, it gives percentages for each spending category by household type.

Data came from Excel and was loaded with Pandas. Format was same as Turkey's, with columns:

- Country
- Year
- Household Type
- Expenditure Type

Data was reshaped with pivot.

- Rows: household types for example single person etc.
- Columns: spending areas for example food alcohol etc.
- Cells: how much each group spent on each area I converted as percent for calculation.

Table 4.1.2.1 – Pivoted Household Expenditure Matrix for U.S. (2011)

Household Type	Food	Housing	Health	Transportation	...
Single person	21.9	30.1	8.2	14.0	...
Married couple w/ kids	20.5	32.0	6.1	16.3	...
Multigenerational	22.8	34.2	5.9	11.5	...

Numbers are percent of money used for each category. Structure is same as Turkish table because I want to compare them. Helps clustering models work on both datasets fairly.

To match U.S. and Turkish categories, some manual edits were done. Things like alcohol, tobacco, eating out were put under Food Entertainment, culture, fun activities were grouped as Entertainment. Tiny or missing categories (like personal care) were deleted or merged. These edits were done by looking at meaning and purpose of each category. Goal was to make sure both datasets speak same "language" in terms of spending types. Even if format looks same, spending habits and priorities differ. Same method was used for both datasets to keep analysis fair and balanced.

4.2. Outlier Treatment and Scaling

After turning data into matrix form with pivot, next step was to check for outliers. Even though values were percentages, some points were too far from others. These rare values could pull cluster centers in wrong direction, especially in K-Means.

To fix this without removing data, Z-score Winsorization was used. Settings were:

- Z-score limit was set to ± 1.7 after testing different options
- Values above $+1.7$ were turned into 1.7
- Values below -1.7 were set to -1.7
- This way, main shape of data stayed same and nothing was deleted

After handling outliers, data was scaled. All spending columns were standardized using Z-score (mean 0, deviation 1). This helped both clustering and PCA work better, since they depend on feature size. It also stopped big categories like housing from taking over model. Same steps were used for both Turkey and U.S. datasets. This helpful for analysis understandable and we can compare them side by side.

Figure 4.2.1. – Distribution of Expenditure Types Before and After Winsorization (Turkey, 2011)

Left side shows raw data. Some categories, like Housing, Food, and Restaurants, with outliers. Right side gives data after Winsorization using ± 1.7 Z-score.

Figure 4.2.2. Boxplot of Expenditure Types in U.S. Households Before and After Winsorization (USA, 2011)

This chart shows how spending seems in U.S. data before and after outlier detection. Left side shows raw data. Some categories for example Housing, Transportation, and Various Goods with outliers. Right side gives data after Winsorization with ± 1.7 Z-score

4.3. Dimensionality Reduction with Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

My data had too many similar parts. Clustering didn't work well like that. So I used fewer features to make it simpler. PCA helped do this. It changed data into new form. Picked two directions with biggest change.

First two components kept most info:

- 74.2% for Turkey
- 76.5% for U.S.

After that:

- Household groups were shown on 2D chart
- K-Means worked better, faster

Process got simpler. Results became easier to read. No big loss in data.

4.4. K-Means Clustering with k=2 and k=3

4.4.1 Results for Turkey (2011)

a) k = 2

K-Means was used on Turkey's 2011 household spending data with k = 2. Before clustering, outliers were reduced by setting Z-scores between -1.7 and +1.7. Then all values were standardized so each spending category had equal impact. To make things simpler, data was also projected into 2D using PCA.

Two groups were found:

Cluster 0 – Basic Needs Focused:

This group includes:

- Couple only
- Couple with children
- Extended family
- One-person
- Other

These households spent more on: food, housing, health, and utilities. They showed a simple and careful spending style.

Cluster 1 – Social and Urban Spenders

Only one household type here:

- Multi-person non-family

This group spent more on things for example entertainment, recreation, transport, and communication. They followed a more social and city-based lifestyle, focused on extras.

Table 4.4.1.1. Cluster Composition Summary for Turkey ($k = 2$)

Cluster Label	Included Household Types	Count
Basic Needs Focused (0)	Couple only, Couple+children, Extended family, One-person, Other	5
Social and Urban Spenders (1)	Multi-person non-family	1

Most household types are in Cluster 0. They show typical spending for example basic needs. Cluster 1 is smaller. I would say it is lifestyle-focused pattern.

Validation Metrics for $k = 2$

Checked results with:

- SS: 0.462
- DBI: 0.332
- CH Index: 5.698
- DI: 1.218

Groups seem okay. SS says most types are in the right place. DBI is low, so clusters don't overlap much. CH and DI say shapes look fine. Overall, $k = 2$ gives a simple but useful split.

b) k = 3

In this part , K-Means was used again on Turkey's 2011 household spending data, this time with k = 3. Same steps were happened like before:

- Winsorization capped Z-scores at ± 1.7
- After data was scaled using z-score normalization
- PCA was used to reduce data to 2D for easier view

Cluster 0 – Basic Needs Focused

Households here spend mostly on musts: food, housing, health. Spending style is simple and based on needs.

- Included types:
 - Couple only
 - Couple with children
 - Extended family

Cluster 1 – Balanced Consumers

These households spend in a more even way—some on basics, some on extras. This shows a balanced and steady lifestyle.

- Included types:
 - One-person
 - Other

Cluster 2 – Social and Urban Spenders

Spending is focused on things like entertainment, transport, and communication. Pattern fits city life and active social routines.

- Included type:
 - Multi-person non-family

Table 4.4.1.2. Cluster Composition Summary for Turkey (k = 3)

Cluster Label	Household Types Included	Count
Basic Needs Focused (0)	Various household types	3
Balanced Consumers (1)	Various household types	2
Social and Urban Spenders (2)	Predominantly urban, non-traditional types	1

Clusters are clearly different. Social group stands out most in how they spend.

Validation Scores (k = 3)

Used same checks again:

- SS: 0.631
- DBI: 0.220
- CH Index: 49.36

These scores are strong. SS shows tight groups with clear space in between. Low DBI means little overlap. CH Index also supports that clusters are compact and well-separated. k = 3 gives solid and detailed view of household spending styles in Turkey.

4.4.2. Clustering Results for U.S. (2011)

a) $k = 2$

K-Means was used on U.S. 2011 household spending data with $k = 2$. To prepare data, same steps were followed as before:

- Z-score Winsorization with ± 1.7 cap to reduce outliers
- Standardization to scale all spending types equally
- PCA used to bring data into 2D for easy view

Cluster 0 – Basic Needs Focused

This group spends more on must-haves like food, housing, and health. Spending style is careful and focused on needs.

Cluster 1 – Social and Urban Spenders

These households put more money into extras like transport, entertainment, and communication. Pattern fits active, city-based lifestyle with less focus on basics.

Table 4.4.2.1. Cluster Composition Summary for U.S. ($k = 2$)

Cluster Label	Description	Count
Basic Needs Focused (0)	Prioritizes essential expenditures	4
Social and Urban Spenders (1)	Allocates more spending to discretionary items	1

Most households are in Cluster 0. Cluster 1 stands out with different spending habits.

Validation Scores (k = 2)

- **SS:** 0.417
- **DBI:** 0.291
- **CH Index:** 4.748
- **DI:** 1.036

These numbers show groups for understand. SS says most points are in right cluster. Low DBI means some distance between groups. CH and DI show shapes are compact but not too close. Overall, k = 2 gives a clear but basic view of U.S. spending styles.

b) k = 3

To see more detail in U.S. household behavior, K-Means was run again with k = 3. Same steps were used:

- Outliers capped at ± 1.7 with Winsorization
- Data scaled with z-scores
- PCA used to bring data into 2D

Cluster 0 – Social and Urban Mix

Includes:

- Couple with children
- Extended family
- Multi-person non-family

These households spend more on things like alcohol, communication, and various goods. Spending shows a mix of urban lifestyle and family needs.

Cluster 1 – Individual Essentials Focused

Includes:

- One-person households

This group spends less on extras. Focus is on basics and saving money.

Cluster 2 – Affluent Couples

Includes:

- Couple only households

This group spends more on leisure and lifestyle items, like alcohol and entertainment. Pattern points to a more relaxed or higher-income lifestyle.

Table 4.4.2.2. Cluster Composition Summary for U.S. (k = 3)

Cluster Label	Included Household Types	Count
Social and Urban Mix (0)	Couple+children, Extended family, Multi-person non-family	3
Individual Essentials (1)	One-person	1
Affluent Couples (2)	Couple only	1

Most households are in Cluster 0. Other two clusters each show a different type of spending behavior.

Validation Scores (k = 3)

To check results:

- SS: 0.355
- DBI: 0.183
- CH Index: 13.15
- DI: 1.245

Even if SS is a bit lower, other scores are strong. Low DBI and high DI show tight, well-separated groups. k = 3 gives meaningful and useful view of how U.S. households spend.

4.5. Cluster Validation Results

To check if clustering made sense, four scores were used for both Turkey and U.S. data (2011):

- **SS** – Shows how well each household fits its group
- **DBI** – Lower is better; means less overlap
- **CH Index** – Higher is better; means clear separation
- **DI** – Measures how far groups are from each other, and how tight they are inside

Table 4.5.1 – Cluster Validation Metrics for Turkey and U.S. (2011)

Dataset	k	SS	DBI	Calinski-Harabasz	DI
Turkey	2	0.462	0.332	5.698	1.218
Turkey	3	0.631	0.220	49.360	2.635
U.S.	2	0.417	0.291	4.748	1.036
U.S.	3	0.355	0.183	13.148	1.245

Summary

Best separation was in Turkey with 3 clusters. SS and DI scores were highest in that part. U.S. also did okay with 3 clusters, especially in DBI. But SS was weaker. Turkey's CH score increased a lot from 2 to 3 clusters, meaning groups became clearer.

Conclusion

Three-cluster models worked for both countries. But Turkey's results were stronger — more stable and better separated.

Note for U.S. ($k = 2$)

Scores show that clusters make sense. SS says most households are in right group. Low DBI means some distance between them. CH and DI also suggest tight and clear shapes. So, $k = 2$ gives a simple but useful view of U.S. spending patterns.

4.6. Visualization of Cluster Structures

4.6.1. Turkey

a) k=2 Turkey

Figure 4.6.1.1. – Cluster Structure of Turkish Households (k = 2)

Chart shows how Turkish households were grouped into 2 clusters. Data was first scaled, then turned into 2D with PCA. Each dot is household type. Blue ones focus on basic needs. Orange one spends more on extras. Black X points center of every group. Results show two main styles of spending: One common and need-based, other mostly lifestyle-focused. Scores at top say groups are clear but not perfect. Still, it's a useful view of how households differ in spending.

Figure 4.6.1.2. – Cluster-Wise Average Standardized Expenditure Shares (Turkey, $k = 2$)

bar chart shows how two household groups in Turkey spend money with different categories. Values are standardized. We can compare them easily. Blue bars spend on basic needs for example food, housing, and furniture. Orange bars spend on extras like transport and restaurants. Difference between two groups is clear. This supports that 2-cluster model takes real spending patterns.

Figure 4.6.1.3. – Distribution of Turkish Households by Cluster (k = 2)

Pie chart shows how households in Turkey are cluster into two groups. Most of them — 83.3% — are in Cluster 0. Only 16.7% are in Cluster 1. This means most households share a similar spending pattern. Cluster 1 is smaller and likely represents a more unique lifestyle.

Figure 4.6.1.4. – Cluster Centers Based on Standardized Expenditure Averages (Turkey, k = 2)

This heatmap shows average spending for each group in Turkey. Colors get darker as spending goes up. Cluster 0 spends more on food, housing, and restaurants. Cluster 1 spends more on alcohol, transport, and some extras. Difference is seems. One group focuses on needs. Other leans mostly lifestyle choices.

Figure 4.6.1.5. – Cluster Sizes by Number of Household Types (Turkey, $k = 2$)

This chart shows how many household types are in each group. Cluster 0 has 5 types. Cluster 1 has only 1. So, most households belong to Cluster 0. Their spending is mostly on basic needs. Cluster 1 is much smaller and shows a different lifestyle. This difference shows that one group is common, while other is more unique.

b) k=3:

Figure 4.6.1.6. Visual representation of Turkish household clusters (k=3) using Principal Component Analysis (PCA).

This plot shows Turkish household types grouped into 3 clusters. Each point is a household type. Data was reduced to 2D using PCA.

Colors show three groups:

- **Blue:** Basic Needs Focused
 - **Orange:** Balanced Consumers
 - **Green:** Social and Urban Spenders
- Black X marks center of each group.

Groups are clearly apart.

Scores at top show strong clustering:

SS = 0.631, DBI = 0.22, Calinski = 49.36, DI = 2.635

As a result, groups are tight, separate, and well-formed.

Figure 4.6.1.7. Scree plot illustrating cumulative explained variance by principal components in Turkish household expenditure dataset (2011).

This line chart shows how much of data is explained by each PCA component. First 2 components explain around 70% of total variance. That means most of important patterns stay visible even after reducing to 2D. So, using 2 components is enough to keep main structure of data.

Figure 4.6.1.8. Bar chart comparing average standardized expenditure shares across three clusters in Turkish dataset ($k=3$).

This chart compares average spending for each group. Bars show how much each cluster spends on different categories. Values are standardized. Cluster 0 spends more on basics like food and housing. Cluster 1 spreads spending more evenly. Cluster 2 spends more on extras like entertainment and lifestyle items. Spending habits clearly change across three groups

Figure 4.6.1.9. Pie Chart Displaying Household Cluster Distribution in Turkey (k=3)

This pie chart shows how households are split across 3 groups. Half of them (50%) are in Basic Needs Focused group. One-third (33.3%) are Social and Urban Spenders. A smaller group (16.7%) are Balanced Consumers. Each group reflects a different way of spending.

Figure 4.6.1.10. Heatmap of Cluster Centers – Standardized Expenditure Averages (Turkey, k=3)

This chart gives a quick look at how each household group spends their money.

- **Group 0** puts most of its budget toward essentials like food and housing.
- **Group 1** spreads its spending more evenly — nothing too high or low.
- **Group 2** leans more toward extras like entertainment and communication.

Darker colors on chart mean more spending in that area. Each cluster clearly reflects a different approach to money use.

Figure 4.6.1.11. Cluster Sizes – Number of Household Types (Turkey, $k=3$)

This bar chart shows how many household types fall into each group. Group 0 (Basic Needs Focused) includes most household types. Group 2 (Social and Urban Spenders) comes next. Group 1 (Balanced Consumers) includes fewest types. Chart gives a quick idea of how common each spending style is in dataset.

4.6.2. United States

A) $k=2$

Figure 4.6.2.1. PCA Scatter Plot of U.S. Households ($k = 2$)

We can see how people in U.S. spend, and who spends in similar ways. After reducing data to two dimensions using PCA, two main patterns stand out: Households on left side tend to share similar, basic-focused spending behaviors — these are Basic Needs Focused group. On right, we see a small cluster that follows a different pattern — likely more socially active or flexible with their spending — referred to here as Social and Urban Spenders. Black X symbols mark center point of each group. Groups are not fully apart, but difference in spending is obvious

Figure 4.6.2.2. Cluster-wise Average Standardized Expenditure Shares (USA, $k = 2$)

Spending patterns between two groups become clear here. Households in blue color (“Basic Needs Focused”) put more of their budget toward essentials like housing, food, and transportation. Those in orange group (“Social and Urban Spenders”) spend a bit more on non-essentials like entertainment and communication. Differences suggest that one group sticks to practical needs, while other leans mostly toward social or lifestyle choices.

Figure 4.6.2.3. Distribution of U.S. Households by Cluster (k = 2)

Pie chart shows how U.S. households are separated. Most of them (80%) are in “Basic Needs Focused” group. These households spend mostly on necessary items. A smaller part (20%) belongs to “Social and Urban Spenders” group, who spend more on things like fun or lifestyle.

Figure 4.6.2.4. Cluster Centers – Standardized Expenditure Averages (U.S., k = 2)

Heatmap shows how each group spends. “Basic Needs Focused” group pays more for housing, transport, and food. “Social and Urban Spenders” spend more on fun and personal items. Darker color is more money spent in this area.

Figure 4.6.2.5. - Cluster Sizes – Number of Household Types (U.S., $k = 2$)

Bar chart shows how many household types belong to each group. Most types are in Cluster 0 (Basic Needs Focused), which means many people spend mostly on daily needs. Only one type is in Cluster 1 (Social and Urban Spenders), a smaller group with a different style.

b) $k=3$

4.6.2.6. PCA Projection of U.S. Household Clusters ($k=3$)

Scatter plot shows how U.S. households group into three clusters after reducing data into two main dimensions. Each dot stands for one household type. Colors show group it belongs to. Black Xs mark center points of groups. Numbers at top tell us groups are clear enough. We can say not perfect, but separated well.

4.6.2.7. Cluster-wise Average Standardized Expenditure Shares for U.S. Households (k=3).

Bar chart shows how three groups of U.S. households spend their money across different categories. All groups spend mostly on housing. Alcohol and education take up smaller parts. Cluster 0 spends more on housing, food, and transport. Clusters 1 and 2 are more balanced, with small differences in things like entertainment and services.

4.6.2.8. Cumulative Explained Variance from PCA for U.S. Household Expenditure Data.

Line chart shows how much total variation is captured as more components are added. First two components explain about 90% of total variance. This means reducing data to two parts still keeps most of it. That's why , using two components for clustering and plots works well.

4.6.2.9. PCA Component Loadings for U.S. Household Expenditure Categories. Heatmap shows how each spending type adds to first two PCA parts. Strong red means it pushes component up. Strong blue means it pulls it down. Health and alcohol shape second part most. Communication, housing, and transport affect first part more by pulling it down.

Distribution of U.S. Households by Cluster (k=3)

4.6.2.10. Distribution of U.S. Households by Cluster (k=3).

Pie chart shows how U.S. household types are grouped into three clusters. Largest group, Social and Urban Mix (60%), mostly includes larger or shared households. Others are Affluent Couples and Individual Essentials, each make up 20%. These groups represent couples and people living alone.

5. Comparing Results

5.1. Comparison of Clustering Results: Turkey vs. U.S.

When we look at household spending groups in Turkey and U.S., we see obvious differences in how groups are formed and what they show us.

In Turkey, using 3 clusters helped to identify spending styles:

- Basic Needs Focused
- Balanced Consumers
- Social and Urban Spenders

These groups were easy to tell separation. Some of them focused more on basics for example food, housing, and health. Also others spent more on extras for example entertainment or communication. Scores from analysis (SS: 0.631 and DI: 2.635) show that these groups were clearly shaped and meaningful. Also, when we looked at what had biggest effect on grouping (through PCA), results made sense and helped us understand behaviors even clear.

U.S. dataset, clustering with $k = 3$ gives three segments:

- Social and Urban Mix
- Individual Essentials
- Affluent Couples

In U.S., groups mostly tell us who lives in house. One group has big families, another has single people, and one has couples without kids. People in these groups spend in similar things. That's why it's really hard to see spending differences. For Turkey, groups show how people use their money in daily life. Some spend mostly on things they need for example food and housing. Others spend more on things they enjoy, like going out or using phones. Numbers like DBI (0.183) and DI (1.245) show that U.S. groups are a bit apart from each other. But SS (0.355) is lower, so groups are not very clear inside. In Turkey, spending styles were mostly crowded. Thanks for this, it was easier to split people into different groups.

Shortly, groups in Turkey show how people choose to spend their money. In U.S., groups mostly tell us who lives together in a home according to their spend. This difference helps people who do research, plan services, or work in business understand daily life better and make more useful decisions.

5.2. Evaluation of k=2 vs. k=3 Segmentations

Trying both 2 and 3 groups gave useful results, especially when we looked at how clear and useful groupings were.

For Turkey:

When we moved from 2 to 3 groups:

- SS went up from 0.462 to 0.631 — this means households in each group became more similar to each other.
- Calinski-Harabasz score jumped from 5.7 to 49.4 — so groups got more separate and better defined.
- DI more than doubled — which means space between groups got wider.

Adding a third group helped. This new group — called "Balanced Consumers" — showed spending habits that sat between those who only spend on needs and those who spend more freely. With just 2 groups, this middle ground was hidden.

For U.S.:

Results were more mixed.

- DBI dropped from 0.291 to 0.183 — a good sign for group separation.
- DI went up a bit (1.036 to 1.245).
- But SS got worse (from 0.417 to 0.355), meaning groups were less tight inside.

With 3 groups, we could see more about household type (like people living alone or as couples), but not much new about how they actually spend. So, if numbers got a little better, new insight wasn't as strong.

In short:

- In Turkey, 3 groups gave us clearer and more useful results.

- In U.S., 3 groups were okay, but didn't add much new meaning — they mostly showed who lives together, not how people spend.

So, choosing number of groups should not only depend on scores, but also on what kind of story data tells us.

5.3. Interpretations and Insights

Clustering results from Turkey and United States gives not just technical segmentation it gives socioeconomic ways that affect how households dominate consumption decisions under different conditions.

- **Spending on Needs vs. Wants**

In US and Turkey one big difference between groups is how much they spend on basic things (like food, housing, health) compared to extras (like entertainment, phones, or alcohol). In Turkey, there's a group that mostly spends on basics. This can happen because their income is lower or they live in bigger families. In U.S., even families with similar budgets still spend more on fun or personal things—especially if it's a couple or someone living alone. So, while both countries show a similar pattern, reasons behind it are different. Local economy, city life, or social help programs might play a role here.

- **Household Type Matters More in U.S.**

In Turkey, spending style matters more than who lives in house. Different types of families can end with in same group if they spend same way. But in U.S., groups mostly match household structure. One-person homes form one group, couples another, and so on. That tells us spending is more linked to lifestyle setup, maybe because people live more independently.

- **Socioeconomic and Policy**

In Turkey, people were grouped by how they spend. That means support can go where it makes most sense. Some might need help with rent or food. Others might need internet or help with studying. In U.S., groups are more about who lives in home. That makes it easier to plan.

Someone who lives alone might need health services. Older couples might need help around house or with using tech.

- **Strategic Industry Applications**

Companies can see from people's group. It helps them give people what they use. For example in Turkey, some spend more on fun or tech. So phones, games, or online shows are a good match. Others care more about basic things. Cheap food or home items can work better for them.

In U.S., it's more about how people live. If someone alone he or she can eat fast-food. Couples can join movies . When brands see these habits, they can offer things that make sense for real life.

6. Conclusion and Future Work

6.1. Summary

This study is about how households in Turkey and U.S. spend money. I used K-Means and PCA to group people based on their spending. Goal was to see if these groups form by how people spend or by who they live with.

Both, using three groups gave better results than using two. In Turkey, groups were clear and made sense. Numbers showed us that groups were strong and well separated.

In Turkey, three groups looked like this:

- People who mostly spend on basics like food and rent (50%)
- People with mixed spending—some needs, some extras (17%)
- People who spend more on fun, travel, or entertainment (33%)

Each group had its own pattern. Some focused on daily needs. Others had more room for extras.

In U.S., three groups looked different. They matched more with who lives in home:

- Mixed households, like families (60%)
- People living alone (20%)

- Couples with no kids (20%)

These groups were not as different in how they spent. Lines between them were softer. U.S. results showed that home type shaped groups more than spending choices.

In both countries, we saw a balance between needs (like food and rent) and wants (like entertainment and phones). But reason behind that balance was different in each place.

In Turkey, in way people spent made difference. In U.S., it was more about how home was maden.

These findings can help in real life. In Turkey, support can be based on what people buy. In U.S., help can focus on who lives in home.

In short, this study showed that tools like K-Means and PCA can group people in helpful ways. But we must always look at local context when we try to understand what groups mean.

6.2. Limitations and for Future

While this study offers good insights into household expenditure separation with clustering technique. I have found some limitations. These limitations also give ways to new directions for future research.

6.2.1. Limitations

This study gave useful ideas about how different households spend their money. But like any study, there are some things that could be improved.

- Few Types of Households:

We only looked at a small number of household types—six from Turkey and five from U.S. This makes it harder to apply results to all families. Especially in U.S., most groups matched household types one-to-one. That means we didn't get to see much about different spending styles.

- Only One Year of Data (2011):

Data came from just 2011. It doesn't show spending changes because of problem like pandemic.

- **No Extra Info About People:**

I only used how much people spent in each category. I didn't include important things like income, education, age, or where they live. If I add these next time, we might get clearer and more useful results.

- **Limits of Method:**

I just used K-Means it was good, but it also has limits. Results can change according to our pick—Sometimes, results react according to method.

6.2.2. Future Recommendations

- **Use More Years of Data:**

Looking at data from just one year does not give entire picture. When later studies use more years of data, we are able to see how individuals' spending patterns change over time and discover broader trends.

- **More Personal Info:**

People spending information is good, but that's not enough. If we also look at things for example income, job, education, or residence. With this informations we can find new things why how people spend money with demographic things.

- **Group People with Other Ways:**

K-Means is a good tool, but we can't to trust on that alone. Other methods for example DBSCAN or GMM—can tell us whether patterns are genuine or purely due to manner in which we classified them.

7. References

Aggarwal, C. C. (2015). *Data Mining*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-14142-8>

- Büyükköz, D. (2010). *Fuzzy Kümeleme Teknikleri ve Avrupa Birliği Üye Ülkeleri ile Türkiye'nin Fuzzy Kümelmesi*.
- Caliński, T., & Harabasz, J. (1974). A Dendrite Method For Cluster Analysis. *Communications in Statistics*, 3(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610927408827101>
- Çatık, A. N., & Karaçuka, M. (2012). A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ALTERNATIVE UNIVARIATE TIME SERIES MODELS IN FORECASTING TURKISH INFLATION. *Journal of Business Economics and Management*, 13(2), 275–293. <https://doi.org/10.3846/16111699.2011.620135>
- Denavas-Walt, C., & Proctor, B. D. (2015). *Income and Poverty in the United States: 2014 Current Population Reports*.
- Dunn, J. E., & Fosdick, R. L. (1974). Thermodynamics, stability, and boundedness of fluids of complexity 2 and fluids of second grade. *Archive for Rational Mechanics and Analysis*, 56(3), 191–252. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00280970>
- Euzenat, J., & Shvaiko, P. (2013). *Ontology Matching*. Springer Berlin Heidelberg. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-38721-0>
- Fu, S., Lu, S. Y., Davies, D. L., & Bouldin, D. W. (1977). The string-to-string correction problem. In *J. Ass. Comput. Mach* (Vol. 1, Issue 2).
- Ghosh, D., & Vogt, A. (n.d.). *Outliers: An Evaluation of Methodologies*. <http://www.itl.nist.gov/>
- Guyeux, C., Chrétien, S., Tayeh, G. B., Demerjian, J., & Bahi, J. (2019). Introducing and comparing recent clustering methods for massive data management in the internet of things. *Journal of Sensor and Actuator Networks*, 8(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/jsan8040056>
- Han, J., Kamber, M., & Pei, J. (2011). *Data Mining. Concepts and Techniques, 3rd Edition (The Morgan Kaufmann Series in Data Management Systems)*.
- Hastie, T., Tibshirani, R., & Friedman, J. (n.d.). *Springer Series in Statistics The Elements of Statistical Learning Data Mining, Inference, and Prediction*.

- Jain, A. K. (2010). Data clustering: 50 years beyond K-means. *Pattern Recognition Letters*, 31(8), 651–666. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.patrec.2009.09.011>
- Jain, A. K., Murty, M. N., & Flynn, P. J. (2000). *Data Clustering: A Review*.
- James, Gareth., Witten, Daniela., Hastie, Trevor., & Tibshirani, Robert. (2017). *An introduction to statistical learning : with applications in R*. Springer : Springer Science+Business Media.
- Jolliffe, I. T., & Cadima, J. (2016). Principal component analysis: a review and recent developments. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 374(2065), 20150202. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2015.0202>
- Kaufman, L., & Rousseeuw, P. J. (1990). *Finding Groups in Data*.
- Kovács, F., Legány, C., & Babos, A. (n.d.). *Cluster Validity Measurement Techniques*.
- Liu, Y., Li, Z., Xiong, H., Gao, X., & Wu, J. (2010). Understanding of Internal Clustering Validation Measures. *2010 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining*, 911–916. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDM.2010.35>
- Lletí, R., Ortiz, M. C., Sarabia, L. A., & Sánchez, M. S. (2004). Selecting variables for k-means cluster analysis by using a genetic algorithm that optimises the silhouettes. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 515(1), 87–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2003.12.020>
- Maguire, H. (2006). *Data quality: concepts, methodologies and techniques*. Scholars Portal.
- Milligan, G. W., & Cooper, M. C. (1985). AN EXAMINATION OF PROCEDURES FOR DETERMINING THE NUMBER OF CLUSTERS IN A DATA SET. In *PSYCHOMETRIKA* (Vol. 50, Issue 2).
- OECD. (n.d.). Household savings. In *Household accounts*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/cfc6f499-en>
- S. B. Kotsiantis, Kanellopoulos, D., & Pintelas, P. E. (2006). data-preprocessing. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF COMPUTER SCIENCE*, 1.
- Shlens, J. (2014). *A Tutorial on Principal Component Analysis*.

Tan, P.-Nin., Steinbach, Michael., & Kumar, Vipin. (2018). *Introduction to data mining*. Pearson.

8. Appendices

Appendix 8.1 – Python Code for Turkey Clustering (k=3)

```
import pandas as pd

import numpy as np

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import seaborn as sns

from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler

from sklearn.decomposition import PCA

from sklearn.cluster import KMeans

from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, silhouette_samples, davies_bouldin_score,
calinski_harabasz_score

sns.set(style="whitegrid")

df = pd.read_excel("Türkiye_2011.xlsx")

df.columns = ["Household Type", "Expenditure Type", "Percentage"]

df["Percentage"] = pd.to_numeric(df["Percentage"], errors="coerce")

df_pivot = df.pivot_table(index="Household Type", columns="Expenditure Type",
values="Percentage")

df_pivot.fillna(df_pivot.mean(), inplace=True)
```

```

z_scores = (df_pivot - df_pivot.mean()) / df_pivot.std()

df_winsorized = df_pivot.mask(z_scores > 1.7, 1.7).mask(z_scores < -1.7, -1.7)

df_melted_before = df_pivot.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

df_melted_after = df_winsorized.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

fig, axes = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(16, 6), sharey=True)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_before, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[0],
palette="Set3")

axes[0].set_title("Before Winsorization")

axes[0].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_after, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[1],
palette="Set3")

axes[1].set_title("After Winsorization (Z > ±1.7 clipped)")

axes[1].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

scaler = StandardScaler()

X_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(df_winsorized)

pca = PCA(n_components=2)

X_pca = pca.fit_transform(X_scaled)

```

```

kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=3, random_state=42, n_init=10)

clusters = kmeans.fit_predict(X_pca)

silhouette_vals = silhouette_samples(X_pca, clusters)

sil_score = silhouette_score(X_pca, clusters)

davies_score = davies_bouldin_score(X_pca, clusters)

calinski_score = calinski_harabasz_score(X_pca, clusters)

centroids = kmeans.cluster_centers_

from sklearn.metrics import pairwise_distances

from scipy.spatial.distance import pdist

def dunn_index(X, labels):

    unique_clusters = np.unique(labels)

    intra_dists = [np.max(pdist(X[labels == c])) for c in unique_clusters if len(X[labels ==
c]) > 1]

    inter_dists = [

        np.min(pairwise_distances(X[labels == i], X[labels == j]))

        for i in unique_clusters for j in unique_clusters if i < j

    ]

    return np.min(inter_dists) / np.max(intra_dists)

dunn_score = dunn_index(X_pca, clusters)

df_result = df_winsorized.copy()

```

```

df_result["PC1"] = X_pca[:, 0]

df_result["PC2"] = X_pca[:, 1]

df_result["Cluster"] = clusters

df_result["Silhouette"] = silhouette_vals

cluster_labels = {

    0: "Basic Needs Focused",

    1: "Balanced Consumers",

    2: "Social and Urban Spenders"

}

df_result["Cluster Label"] = df_result["Cluster"].map(cluster_labels)

print(f'Silhouette Score: {sil_score:.3f}')

print(f'Davies-Bouldin Index: {davies_score:.2f}')

print(f'Calinski-Harabasz Index: {calinski_score:.2f}')

print(f'Dunn Index: {dunn_score:.3f}')

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 7))

palette = ['#3498DB', '#F39C12', '#2ECC71']

for i, label in enumerate(cluster_labels.values()):

    plt.scatter(

        df_result[df_result["Cluster Label"] == label]["PC1"],

        df_result[df_result["Cluster Label"] == label]["PC2"],

```

```

        c=palette[i],

        s=200,

        edgecolors='black',

        linewidths=1.2,

        label=label

    )

plt.scatter(centroids[:, 0], centroids[:, 1], c='black', s=300, marker='X', label="Centroids")

plt.title(

    f"Turkey 2011 - PCA + KMeans Clustering (k=3)\n"

    f"Silhouette: {sil_score:.3f} | Davies-Bouldin: {davies_score:.2f} | "

    f"Calinski: {calinski_score:.2f} | Dunn: {dunn_score:.3f}"

)

plt.xlabel("Principal Component 1")

plt.ylabel("Principal Component 2")

plt.legend()

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

pca = PCA()

X_pca_full = pca.fit_transform(X_scaled)

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))

plt.plot(range(1, len(pca.explained_variance_ratio_)+1),

         np.cumsum(pca.explained_variance_ratio_)*100, marker='o')

plt.xticks(range(1, len(pca.explained_variance_ratio_)+1))

plt.xlabel("Number of Components")

plt.ylabel("Cumulative Explained Variance (%)")

plt.title("PCA – Cumulative Explained Variance (Turkey)")

plt.grid(True)

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

pca = PCA(n_components=2)

pca.fit(X_scaled)

```

```

loadings = pd.DataFrame(pca.components_.T,

                       columns=['PC1', 'PC2'],

                       index=df_winsorized.columns)

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))

sns.heatmap(loadings, annot=True, cmap='coolwarm', center=0)

plt.title("PCA Component Loadings (Turkey)")

```

```
plt.xlabel("Principal Components")
```

```
plt.ylabel("Expenditure Types")
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
plt.show()
```

```
cluster_means =  
df_result.groupby("Cluster").mean(numeric_only=True).drop(columns=["PC1",  
"PC2",  
"Silhouette"], errors="ignore")
```

```
cluster_means.T.plot(kind="bar", figsize=(12, 6), width=0.7, color=palette)
```

```
plt.title("Cluster-wise Average Standardized Expenditure Shares (Turkey, k=3)")
```

```
plt.xlabel("Expenditure Type")
```

```
plt.ylabel("Z-Score (Standardized)")
```

```
plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")
```

```
plt.legend(title="Cluster", bbox_to_anchor=(1.01, 1), loc="upper left")
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
plt.show()
```

```
named_labels = {
```

```
    0: "Basic Needs Focused",
```

```
    1: "Balanced Consumers",
```

```
    2: "Social and Urban Spenders"
```

```
}
```

```
83
```

```

named_counts = df_result["Cluster"].map(named_labels).value_counts().sort_index()

plt.figure(figsize=(7, 7))

plt.pie(

    named_counts,

    labels=[f"{name} ({percent:.1f}%)" for name, percent in zip(named_counts.index, 100 *
named_counts / named_counts.sum())],

    startangle=140,

    colors=[palette[i] for i in sorted(named_labels.keys())]

)

plt.title("Distribution of Turkish Households by Cluster (k=3)")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))

sns.heatmap(cluster_means, annot=True, cmap="YlGnBu", fmt=".2f")

plt.title("Cluster Centers – Standardized Expenditure Averages (Turkey, k=3)")

plt.xlabel("Expenditure Types")

plt.ylabel("Cluster")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

label_names = {

```

```

0: "Cluster 0\n(Basic Needs Focused)",
1: "Cluster 1\n(Balanced Consumers)",
2: "Cluster 2\n(Social and Urban Spenders)"
}

cluster_labels_named = df_result["Cluster"].map(label_names)

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))

cluster_labels_named.value_counts().sort_index().plot(kind="barh", color=[palette[i] for i in
sorted(label_names.keys())])

plt.xlabel("Number of Household Types")

plt.ylabel("Cluster")

plt.title("Cluster Sizes – Number of Household Types (Turkey, k=3)")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

```

Appendix 8.2 – Python Code for Turkey Clustering (k=2)

```

import pandas as pd

import numpy as np

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import seaborn as sns

from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler

```

```

from sklearn.decomposition import PCA

from sklearn.cluster import KMeans

from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, silhouette_samples, davies_bouldin_score,
calinski_harabasz_score

from sklearn.metrics import pairwise_distances

from scipy.spatial.distance import pdist

sns.set(style="whitegrid")

df = pd.read_excel("Türkiye_2011.xlsx")

df.columns = ["Household Type", "Expenditure Type", "Percentage"]

df["Percentage"] = pd.to_numeric(df["Percentage"], errors="coerce")

df_pivot = df.pivot_table(index="Household Type", columns="Expenditure Type",
values="Percentage")

df_pivot.fillna(df_pivot.mean(), inplace=True)

z_scores = (df_pivot - df_pivot.mean()) / df_pivot.std()

df_winsorized = df_pivot.mask(z_scores > 1.7, 1.7).mask(z_scores < -1.7, -1.7)

df_melted_before = df_pivot.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

df_melted_after = df_winsorized.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

fig, axes = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(16, 6), sharey=True)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_before, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[0],
palette="Set3")

```

```

axes[0].set_title("Before Winsorization")

axes[0].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_after, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[1],
palette="Set3")

axes[1].set_title("After Winsorization (Z > ±1.7 clipped)")

axes[1].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

scaler = StandardScaler()

X_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(df_winsorized)

pca = PCA(n_components=2)

X_pca = pca.fit_transform(X_scaled)

kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=2, random_state=42, n_init=10)

clusters = kmeans.fit_predict(X_pca)

silhouette_vals = silhouette_samples(X_pca, clusters)

sil_score = silhouette_score(X_pca, clusters)

davies_score = davies_bouldin_score(X_pca, clusters)

calinski_score = calinski_harabasz_score(X_pca, clusters)

centroids = kmeans.cluster_centers_

def dunn_index(X, labels):

```

```

unique_clusters = np.unique(labels)

intra_dists = [np.max(pdist(X[labels == c])) for c in unique_clusters if len(X[labels ==
c]) > 1]

inter_dists = [

    np.min(pairwise_distances(X[labels == i], X[labels == j]))

    for i in unique_clusters for j in unique_clusters if i < j

]

return np.min(inter_dists) / np.max(intra_dists)

dunn = dunn_index(X_pca, clusters)

df_result = df_winsorized.copy()

df_result["PC1"] = X_pca[:, 0]

df_result["PC2"] = X_pca[:, 1]

df_result["Cluster"] = clusters

df_result["Silhouette"] = silhouette_vals

cluster_labels = {

    0: "Basic Needs Focused",

    1: "Social and Urban Spenders"

}

df_result["Cluster Label"] = df_result["Cluster"].map(cluster_labels)

metrics_df = pd.DataFrame({

```

```

    "Metric": ["Silhouette Score", "Davies-Bouldin Index", "Calinski-Harabasz Index", "Dunn
Index"],

    "Value": [sil_score, davies_score, calinski_score, dunn]

})

print(metrics_df)

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 7))

palette = ['#3498DB', '#F39C12']

for i, label in enumerate(cluster_labels.values()):

    plt.scatter(

        df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == i]["PC1"],

        df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == i]["PC2"],

        c=palette[i],

        s=200,

        edgecolors='black',

        linewidths=1.2,

        label=label

    )

plt.scatter(centroids[:, 0], centroids[:, 1], c='black', s=300, marker='X', label="Centroids")

plt.title(

    f'Clustering of Turkish Households (k=2)\n"

```

```

f'Silhouette: {sil_score:.3f} | Davies-Bouldin: {davies_score:.2f} | "
f'Calinski: {calinski_score:.2f} | Dunn: {dunn:.2f}'
)

plt.xlabel("Principal Component 1")

plt.ylabel("Principal Component 2")

plt.legend()

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

import seaborn as sns

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 7))

palette = ['#3498DB', '#F39C12']

for cluster in df_result["Cluster"].unique():

    plt.scatter(

        df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == cluster]["PC1"],

        df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == cluster]["PC2"],

        c=palette[cluster],

        s=200,

        edgecolors='black',

        linewidths=1.2,

```

```

        label=f'Cluster {cluster}'

    )

plt.scatter(

    centroids[:, 0], centroids[:, 1],

    c='black', s=300, marker='X', label="Centroids", edgecolors='white'

)

plt.title("PCA Scatter Plot of Turkish Households (k=2)")

plt.xlabel("Principal Component 1")

plt.ylabel("Principal Component 2")

plt.legend()

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

cluster_means =
df_result.groupby("Cluster").mean(numeric_only=True).drop(columns=["PC1", "PC2",
"Silhouette"], errors="ignore")

cluster_means.T.plot(kind="bar", figsize=(12, 6), width=0.7, color=palette)

plt.title("Cluster-wise Average Standardized Expenditure Shares (Turkey, k=2)")

plt.xlabel("Expenditure Type")

plt.ylabel("Z-Score (Standardized)")

```

```

plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")

plt.legend(title="Cluster", bbox_to_anchor=(1.01, 1), loc="upper left")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

cluster_counts = df_result["Cluster"].value_counts().sort_index()

plt.figure(figsize=(6, 6))

plt.pie(

    cluster_counts,

    labels=[f"Cluster {i}" for i in cluster_counts.index],

    autopct='%1.1f%%',

    startangle=140,

    colors=[palette[i] for i in cluster_counts.index]

)

plt.title("Distribution of Turkish Households by Cluster (k=2)")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))

sns.heatmap(cluster_means, annot=True, cmap="YlGnBu", center=0, linewidths=0.5,
fmt=".2f")

plt.title("Cluster Centers – Standardized Expenditure Averages (Turkey, k=2)")

```

```

plt.xlabel("Expenditure Types")

plt.ylabel("Cluster")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

cluster_assignments = {

    0: ["Couple only", "Couple with children", "Extended family", "One-person", "Other"],

    1: ["Multi-person non-family"]

}

df_assignments = pd.DataFrame([

    {"Cluster": 0, "Label": "Basic Needs Focused", "Household Types": "",

    ".join(cluster_assignments[0])},

    {"Cluster": 1, "Label": "Social and Urban Spenders", "Household Types": "",

    ".join(cluster_assignments[1])}

])

print(df_assignments.to_string(index=False))

plt.figure(figsize=(7, 4))

cluster_counts.sort_index().plot(kind="barh", color=["#3498DB", "#F39C12"])

plt.xlabel("Number of Household Types")

plt.ylabel("Cluster")

plt.title("Cluster Sizes – Number of Household Types (Turkey, k=2)")

```

```
plt.yticks([0, 1], ["Cluster 0\n(Basic Needs Focused)", "Cluster 1\n(Social and Urban Spenders)"])
```

```
plt.grid(axis='x', linestyle='--', alpha=0.7)
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
plt.show()
```

Appendix 8.3 – Python Code for U.S. Clustering (k=3)

```
import pandas as pd
```

```
import numpy as np
```

```
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

```
import seaborn as sns
```

```
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
```

```
from sklearn.decomposition import PCA
```

```
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
```

```
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, davies_bouldin_score, calinski_harabasz_score, pairwise_distances
```

```
from scipy.spatial.distance import pdist
```

```
sns.set(style="whitegrid")
```

```
plt.rcParams['figure.figsize'] = (12, 8)
```

```
df = pd.read_excel("ABD_Harcama_Yuzdeleri_SonDuzen.xlsx")
```

```
df.columns = ["Household Type", "Expenditure Type", "Percentage"]
```

```

df["Percentage"] = pd.to_numeric(df["Percentage"], errors="coerce")

df_pivot = df.pivot_table(index="Household Type", columns="Expenditure Type",
values="Percentage")

df_pivot.fillna(df_pivot.mean(), inplace=True)

z_scores = np.abs((df_pivot - df_pivot.mean()) / df_pivot.std())

df_winsorized = df_pivot.mask(z_scores > 1.7, 1.7).mask(z_scores < -1.7, -1.7)

df_melted_before = df_pivot.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

df_melted_after = df_winsorized.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

fig, axes = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(18, 6), sharey=True)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_before, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[0],
palette="Set3")

axes[0].set_title("Before Winsorization")

axes[0].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_after, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[1],
palette="Set3")

axes[1].set_title("After Winsorization (Z > ±1.7 clipped)")

axes[1].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

scaler = StandardScaler()

```

```

X_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(df_winsorized)

pca = PCA(n_components=2)

X_pca = pca.fit_transform(X_scaled)

k = 3

kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=k, random_state=42, n_init=10)

labels = kmeans.fit_predict(X_pca)

centroids = kmeans.cluster_centers_

sil_score = silhouette_score(X_pca, labels)

davies_score = davies_bouldin_score(X_pca, labels)

calinski_score = calinski_harabasz_score(X_pca, labels)

def dunn_index(X, labels):

    unique_clusters = np.unique(labels)

    intra_dists = [np.max(pdist(X[labels == c])) for c in unique_clusters if len(X[labels ==
c]) > 1]

    inter_dists = [

        np.min(pairwise_distances(X[labels == i], X[labels == j]))

        for i in unique_clusters for j in unique_clusters if i < j

    ]

    return np.min(inter_dists) / np.max(intra_dists)

dunn = dunn_index(X_pca, labels)

```

```

df_result = df_winsorized.copy()

df_result["PC1"] = X_pca[:, 0]

df_result["PC2"] = X_pca[:, 1]

df_result["Cluster"] = labels

cluster_means = df_result.groupby("Cluster").mean(numeric_only=True)

cluster_means = cluster_means.drop(columns=["PC1", "PC2"], errors="ignore")

print(cluster_means)

print("\nKümeleme Geçerlilik Metrikleri:")

print(f"Silhouette Score      : {sil_score:.4f}")

print(f"Davies-Bouldin Index    : {davies_score:.4f}")

print(f"Calinski-Harabasz Index : {calinski_score:.4f}")

print(f"Dunn Index              : {dunn:.4f}")

palette = ['#3498DB', '#F39C12', '#2ECC71']

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 7))

for cluster in range(k):

    plt.scatter(

        df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == cluster]["PC1"],

        df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == cluster]["PC2"],

        c=palette[cluster], s=200, edgecolors='black', linewidths=1.2, label=f'Cluster {cluster}'

    )

```

```

plt.scatter(centroids[:, 0], centroids[:, 1],

            c='black', s=300, marker='X', label="Centroids", edgecolors='white')

plt.title(

    f"PCA + KMeans (k=3)\nSilhouette: {sil_score:.3f} | Davies-Bouldin: {davies_score:.2f} |

"

    f"Calinski: {calinski_score:.2f} | Dunn: {dunn:.2f}"

)

plt.xlabel("Principal Component 1")

plt.ylabel("Principal Component 2")

plt.legend()

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

cluster_means.T.plot(kind="bar", figsize=(12, 6), width=0.75, color=palette)

plt.title("Cluster-wise Average Standardized Expenditure Shares")

plt.xlabel("Expenditure Type")

plt.ylabel("Z-Score (Standardized)")

plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")

plt.legend(title="Cluster", bbox_to_anchor=(1.01, 1), loc="upper left")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

```

```

cluster_counts = df_result["Cluster"].value_counts()

plt.figure(figsize=(6, 6))

plt.pie(

    cluster_counts,

    labels=[f'Cluster {i}' for i in cluster_counts.index],

    autopct='%1.1f%%',

    startangle=140,

    colors=[palette[i] for i in cluster_counts.index]

)

plt.title("Distribution of U.S. Households by Cluster")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

df_result["Household Type"] = df_pivot.index

n_clusters = df_result["Cluster"].nunique()

print(f"Toplam {n_clusters} farklı küme tespit edildi.\n")

cluster_summary = df_result.groupby("Cluster")["Household Type"].apply(list)

print("Kümelere göre Household Type listesi:\n")

print(cluster_summary)

print("\nHer kümede kaç örnek var (küme boyutları):\n")

print(df_result["Cluster"].value_counts().sort_index())

```

```

summary_df = df_result[["Household Type", "Cluster"]].sort_values(by="Cluster")

print("\nTüm Household Type'ların küme atamaları:\n")

print(summary_df)

pca = PCA()

X_pca_full_us = pca.fit_transform(X_scaled)

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))

plt.plot(range(1, len(pca.explained_variance_ratio_)+1),

         np.cumsum(pca.explained_variance_ratio_)*100, marker='o')

plt.xticks(range(1, len(pca.explained_variance_ratio_)+1))

plt.xlabel("Number of Components")

plt.ylabel("Cumulative Explained Variance (%)")

plt.title("PCA – Cumulative Explained Variance (USA)")

plt.grid(True)

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

pca = PCA(n_components=2)

pca.fit(X_scaled)

loadings_us = pd.DataFrame(pca.components_.T,

                           columns=['PC1', 'PC2'],

                           index=df_winsorized.columns)

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))

sns.heatmap(loadings_us, annot=True, cmap='coolwarm', center=0)

plt.title("PCA Component Loadings (USA)")

plt.xlabel("Principal Components")

plt.ylabel("Expenditure Types")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

cluster_names_usa = {

    0: "Social and Urban Mix",

    1: "Individual Essentials",

    2: "Affluent Couples"

}

df_result["Cluster Name"] = df_result["Cluster"].map(cluster_names_usa)

cluster_named_counts = df_result["Cluster Name"].value_counts()

plt.figure(figsize=(6, 6))

plt.pie(

    cluster_named_counts,

    labels=[f" {label} ({perc:.1f}%" for label, perc in zip(cluster_named_counts.index, 100 *
cluster_named_counts / cluster_named_counts.sum())],

    colors=[palette[list(cluster_names_usa.keys())[list(cluster_names_usa.values()).index(name)]]
for name in cluster_named_counts.index],
101

```

```
startangle=140
)
plt.title("Distribution of U.S. Households by Cluster (k=3)")
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Appendix 8.4. – Python Code for U.S. Clustering (k=2)

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
from sklearn.preprocessing import StandardScaler
from sklearn.decomposition import PCA
from sklearn.cluster import KMeans
from sklearn.metrics import silhouette_score, silhouette_samples, davies_bouldin_score,
calinski_harabasz_score
from sklearn.metrics import pairwise_distances
from scipy.spatial.distance import pdist
sns.set(style="whitegrid")
df = pd.read_excel("ABD_Harcama_Yuzdeleri_SonDuzen.xlsx")
```

```

df.columns = ["Household Type", "Expenditure Type", "Percentage"]

df_pivot = df.pivot_table(index="Household Type", columns="Expenditure Type",
values="Percentage")

df_pivot.fillna(df_pivot.mean(), inplace=True)

z_scores = np.abs((df_pivot - df_pivot.mean()) / df_pivot.std())

df_winsorized = df_pivot.mask(z_scores > 1.7, 1.7).mask(z_scores < -1.7, -1.7)

df_melted_before = df_pivot.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

df_melted_after = df_winsorized.reset_index().melt(id_vars="Household Type",
var_name="Expenditure Type", value_name="Percentage")

fig, axes = plt.subplots(1, 2, figsize=(18, 6), sharey=True)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_before, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[0],
palette="Set3")

axes[0].set_title("Before Winsorization")

axes[0].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

sns.boxplot(data=df_melted_after, x="Expenditure Type", y="Percentage", ax=axes[1],
palette="Set3")

axes[1].set_title("After Winsorization (Z > ±1.7 clipped)")

axes[1].tick_params(axis='x', rotation=45)

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

scaler = StandardScaler()

```

```

X_scaled = scaler.fit_transform(df_winsorized)

pca = PCA(n_components=2)

X_pca = pca.fit_transform(X_scaled)

kmeans = KMeans(n_clusters=2, random_state=42, n_init=10)

clusters = kmeans.fit_predict(X_pca)

silhouette_vals = silhouette_samples(X_pca, clusters)

sil_score = silhouette_score(X_pca, clusters)

davies_score = davies_bouldin_score(X_pca, clusters)

calinski_score = calinski_harabasz_score(X_pca, clusters)

centroids = kmeans.cluster_centers_

def dunn_index(X, labels):

    unique_clusters = np.unique(labels)

    intra_dists = [np.max(pdist(X[labels == c])) for c in unique_clusters if len(X[labels ==
c]) > 1]

    inter_dists = [

        np.min(pairwise_distances(X[labels == i], X[labels == j]))

        for i in unique_clusters for j in unique_clusters if i < j

    ]

    return np.min(inter_dists) / np.max(intra_dists)

```

```

dunn = dunn_index(X_pca, clusters)

df_result = df_winsorized.copy()

df_result["PC1"] = X_pca[:, 0]

df_result["PC2"] = X_pca[:, 1]

df_result["Cluster"] = clusters

df_result["Silhouette"] = silhouette_vals

cluster_labels = {

    0: "Basic Needs Focused",

    1: "Social and Urban Spenders"

}

df_result["Cluster Label"] = df_result["Cluster"].map(cluster_labels)

metrics_df = pd.DataFrame({

    "Metric": ["Silhouette Score", "Davies-Bouldin Index", "Calinski-Harabasz Index", "Dunn
Index"],

    "Value": [sil_score, davies_score, calinski_score, dunn]

})

print(metrics_df)

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 7))

palette = ['#3498DB', '#F39C12']

for i, label in enumerate(cluster_labels.values()):

```

```

plt.scatter(

    df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == i]["PC1"],

    df_result[df_result["Cluster"] == i]["PC2"],

    c=palette[i],

    s=200,

    edgecolors='black',

    linewidths=1.2,

    label=label

)

plt.scatter(centroids[:, 0], centroids[:, 1], c='black', s=300, marker='X', label="Centroids")

plt.title(

    f"Clustering of U.S. Households (k=2)\n"

    f"Silhouette: {sil_score:.3f} | Davies-Bouldin: {davies_score:.2f} | "

    f"Calinski: {calinski_score:.2f} | Dunn: {dunn:.2f}"

)

plt.xlabel("Principal Component 1")

plt.ylabel("Principal Component 2")

plt.legend()

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

```

```

cluster_means = df_result.groupby("Cluster Label").mean(numeric_only=True)

cluster_means.drop(columns=["PC1", "PC2", "Silhouette", "Cluster"], inplace=True)

cluster_means.T.plot(kind="bar", figsize=(12, 6), width=0.7, color=palette)

plt.title("Cluster-wise Average Standardized Expenditure Shares (USA)")

plt.xlabel("Expenditure Type")

plt.ylabel("Z-Score (Standardized)")

plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")

plt.legend(title="Cluster", bbox_to_anchor=(1.01, 1), loc="upper left")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

cluster_counts = df_result["Cluster Label"].value_counts()

plt.figure(figsize=(6, 6))

plt.pie(cluster_counts, labels=cluster_counts.index, autopct='%1.1f%%', startangle=140,
        colors=palette)

plt.title("Distribution of U.S. Households by Cluster")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

cluster_counts = df_result.reset_index().groupby("Cluster")["Household Type"].nunique()

print(cluster_counts)

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(10, 6))

sns.heatmap(cluster_means, annot=True, cmap="YlGnBu", fmt=".2f")

plt.title("Cluster Centers – Standardized Expenditure Averages (USA, k=2)")

plt.xlabel("Expenditure Types")

plt.ylabel("Cluster")

plt.tight_layout()

plt.show()

label_names = {

    0: "Cluster 0\n(Basic Needs Focused)",

    1: "Cluster 1\n(Social and Urban Spenders)"

}

cluster_labels_named = df_result["Cluster"].map(label_names)

```

```

plt.figure(figsize=(8, 5))

cluster_labels_named.value_counts().sort_index().plot(

    kind="barh",

    color=[palette[i] for i in sorted(label_names.keys())]

)

plt.xlabel("Number of Household Types")

plt.ylabel("Cluster")

```

```
plt.title("Cluster Sizes – Number of Household Types (USA, k=2)")
```

```
plt.tight_layout()
```

```
plt.show()
```

8.5. Data Sources

8.5.1. Data Source for Turkey

- **Source file:** hanehalki tipinin hanehalki tuketim harcamasinin turlerine gore dagilimi.xls
- **Original source:** Turkish Statistical Institute (TÜİK),

<https://data.tuik.gov.tr/Bulten/Index?p=Hanehalki-Tuketim-Harcamasi-2023-53801>

8.5.1. Data Source for U.S.

- **Source file:** cusize.xls
- **Original source:** U.S. Bureau of Labor Statistics (BLS),
<https://www.bls.gov/cex/2011/Standard/cusize.pdf>